

Artificial Intelligence to Improve Effectiveness in Education and Health Sector-with Special Reference to Stanford University's use is Medical Sciences

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Introduction

The theory and development of computer systems which has the ability to perform tasks very similar to human intelligence such as speech recognition, language translation, Learning, planning, problem-solving, etc is artificial intelligence. It is also called as machine intelligence.

John McCarthy, a computer scientist, is one of the founding fathers of artificial intelligence, together with Marvin Minsky, Allen Newell and Herbert A. Simon.

John McCarthy coined the term artificial intelligence.

Statement of the Problem

Whether artificial intelligence has applicability in education and health sector?

Objectives of the study

1. To ascertain the importance of artificial intelligence in education sector
2. To analyze the practical applicability of artificial intelligence in education and health sector—with special reference to Stanford university applications in medical field.

Research methodology

- The researcher has made use of secondary data
- This research is an exploratory research
- Source of secondary data—books, magazines and relevant websites from internet.

Limitations of the study

As this study is based on secondary data available—it lacks the effectiveness of clarity that is made possible and available in primary data

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Education Sector and Health Sector

Education Sector

Application of artificial intelligence technology in wide range of application is amazing. As we all know, androids have helped us to live a better life in our day to day activities. Artificial intelligence can make a big change in education sector. It has already made significant changes in health sector, helping doctors diagnose serious diseases accurately which could help them to prescribe appropriate medicines.

It is apparent that computer intelligence would take over in education sector, helping the teachers and the students save time and efforts in learning process. It is very difficult for an educator to help each and every student with their individual educational need, to discover their potential, their problems and their personality. It is very difficult in a class of 50 or 60 to pay individual attention to assess their performance.

Machine –learning algorithms have already begun helping teachers to assess which subject's students are struggling the most to work out a plan for their betterment.

The following are some aspects that highlight the EFFECTIVENESS of artificial intelligence in education sector

Grading and Assessment

Teachers would elevate their knowledge standards if they could spare sufficient time for preparing for the class, like reading books, and journals and take up the research work instead of spending huge amount of time in grading homework and tests particularly if, it is repetitive in nature and involve addressing large lecture classroom. Objective type assessments like multiple choice questions, fill in the blanks, can be effectively done by machines. As essay grading software is still in its infancy, so teachers could spare time only for the types of activities which cannot be done by machines and focus more on student interaction than grading

Plagiarism checkers: TURNITIN, a popular tool used by instructors to analyze students' writing for plagiarism. artificial intelligence can be used for detecting plagiarism.

Robo-readers: Essay grading is very tedious work which involves more use of labour so teachers can make use of Robo-readers.

Glimpse into the future: Artificial intelligence can be tailored to each student's individual strengths and weaknesses. Machine –learning can be effective in identifying weak students at an early stage to divert extra resources and time on those students.

Fraud prevention: Daily transactions in banks and financial institutions are so huge that it becomes manually impossible to review each aspect. artificial intelligence is used to create systems that surfaces what types of transactions are fraudulent.

Guide to the Teacher and The Student

COURSERA, a massive online course provider is already helping in this regard. When a large number of students are found to submit the wrong answer to an assignment given to them, this system of software alerts the teacher and gives future students a customized message that would hint to the right answer. students need not wait for the professor to receive feedback. They get immediate feedback so that they can understand the concept and learn to do it correctly the next time.

Additional Support from Artificial Intelligence

Some tutoring programmes can effectively help students in learning basic mathematics, English and physics. Fundamental concepts can be easily learnt through artificial intelligence so that high

order learning can be taken up by teachers to facilitate. With the type of technological advancement that is happening even high-order learning also can be taken up by machines in future.

Artificial Intelligence has the Capacity to Find and Interact with Information

Artificial intelligent systems affect the information we have on daily basis. GOOGLE adapts results to users based on location, AMAZON, makes recommendations based on previous purchases, SIRI, adapts to your needs and commands and all the web ads are directed towards your interests and shopping preferences. Artificial intelligence based systems with more integrated technology has already been doing a good job to help learners to interact with existing information.

Teachers are No More Teachers, They are Facilitators

A facilitator is one who facilitates learning by helping a group of people with common objective or goal. Teacher, as a facilitator takes the lead and assumes responsibility to guide the group

A teacher for this purpose should possess good communication skills, active listening skills, rapport building- enhance confidence level, so that the group accept them as their leader, and develop synergy by good team work. Teacher's responsibility would be to confine only to plan, guide and manage the group, understand their objectives and facilitate learning. Rather than grading homework's, correcting assignments which consume a lot of time and can easily be taken over by artificial intelligence.

Educational Software Can be Adopted to Student Needs

Adaptive learning programmes help students by responding to their needs, putting greater emphasis on important topics, constant repetition of difficult ones, and help students to learn them.

These types of customized education standards could be a machine –assisted solution to help students in a classroom, with teachers as facilitators to help them by their support.

Artificial Intelligence Make Trial and Error Learning Less Scary

There may be a negative impact on the psychology of students when they fail to do a particular task. They may not try again as it may bring down their confidence levels. With artificial intelligence in use students learn to deal with trial and error in a more judgment free environment especially when AI tutors can offer solutions for improvement. It is inferred that artificial intelligence systems themselves would learn by trial and error method

Smart Content Kit

Artificial intelligence helps to collect and divide textbook content into small 'smart' kits that can include summaries, multiple choice objective type practice tests etc.

Virtual Facilitators and Learning Environment

It is difficult to replace a human force who can think, act, react and interact like virtual humans. Response is an important and integral part of learning process but with artificial intelligence being the first step to initiate change, university of southern California (USC) institute for creative technologies have a number of ongoing projects in space that make our dream a reality.

Paving New Learning Pathways in the Coming Decade

Understanding responsibility and adaptability are the human like attributes which are very important for human interaction though slow. Artificial intelligence has been instrumental in developing these qualities.

Effective implementation of artificial intelligence in education sector

ACCORDING TO 2016 REPORT, 86% of health care providers, life science companies and technology vendors to health care are using artificial intelligence technology

Importance of Artificial intelligence in health care is as follows

To Store Important Data- Medical records and past history of the patients are managed well by artificial intelligence. Robots collect, store, re format and trace data to provide data faster

Repetitive Work -Robots can accurately take up the tasks like analyzing tests, X-rays CT scans etc., particularly in cardiology and radiology .Artificial intelligence can take up these tasks sparing doctors to concentrate only on complicated cases where effective supervision is required.

Digital Consultation -Apps like Babylon in U.K use artificial intelligence to give medical consultation. Users report their symptoms to the app, which uses speech recognition to compare against a data base of illnesses. Babylon then offers a solution depending upon the patient’s medical history

Medical Supervision -The national institute of health has created the Aicure app to monitor the use of medication by a patient. A smart phones webcam is partnered with artificial intelligence to confirm to the doctors that patients are taking medicines timely.

Health Care System Analysis -In Netherlands’ 97% of the health care invoices are digital. A Dutch company uses artificial intelligence to sift through the data to highlight mistakes in treatments, work inefficiency etc.

Practical Applicability of Artificial Intelligence by Stanford University Scientists

A paper was presented on JULY 10,2018, meeting of JURE LESKOVEC, an associate professor of computer science, along with two other students describe that artificial intelligence can help in predicting potential side effects of drug combinations .

That system called Decagon, could help doctors make better decision regarding prescription of drugs and help researchers find better combination of drugs to treat complex diseases.

Decagon's predictions would be more accurate in future as presently it is not available to many doctors in more user friendly form.

To test the effectiveness of Decagon, the researchers group looked to find out if decagon could make accurate predictions. In many cases, the predictions were accurate

For example: there was no indication in the team's data that the combination of atorvastatin, a cholesterol drug, and amlodipine, a blood pressure medication could lead to muscle inflammation. Yet Decagon predicted that it would, and it was right.

Although this did not figure in original data, a case report from 2017 suggested that the drug combination had led to a dangerous kind of muscle inflammation.

When Stanford computer scientists searched for medical explanation for evidence of 10 side effects predicted by Decagon but not in the original data, the team members found that five out of ten have been confirmed. This would further encourage Decagon's predictions.

Decagon has confined itself only to predict the possible side effects of a pair of drugs. In future, expectations are to extend its predictions even to prescribe doctors., a more user friendly tool to reduce the impact of drug use to only a fewer side effect.

Decagon is (a kind of artificial intelligence modelled after the brain) that was developed by Stanford university computer scientists to help doctors take better decisions about which drugs to prescribe to minimize the possible side effects of a drug.

Findings and Suggestions

Artificial intelligence can be used In education sector as it saves time for teachers, guides both students and teachers .With the development of artificial intelligence teachers are now facilitators so that they save their quality time to enhance their knowledge and skills. But, there are some serious difficulties in using artificial intelligence like

Artificial intelligence can predict wrong conclusions with confidence which is dangerous.

Artificial intelligence cannot deal with situations if there are not programmed for the same. They do not register aspects which were never experienced before, as they reserve their judgements on past experience.

The programmer of the machine intelligence should be efficient .otherwise the system breaks down.

Artificial intelligence does not have universal application it works for somethings and is completely useless for other things.it is not applicable at all times for eg: biometric systems, if you smear wax on your finger, the machine will not accept it.

So its use has to be monitored so that 'would work like a stick in our hand making commands at our instruction rather than a stick we hold to lean on where it has complete control over us.

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence in education as well as in health sector would enhance the ability to reason and when machines and humans work together there would be greater efficiency and productivity.

Machines would do the computational work while leaving other tasks to human beings so that the best results would occur with this combination. For e.g.in the field of medical diagnosis, machines produce diagnosis for the patients and describe the problem along with recommendations for the follow up treatment plan. Based on the data, furnished by machines ,doctors can prescribe medicines and work out appropriate treatment plan for diseases.